

NURSING STAFF IN NEUROLOGICAL EMERGENCIES: PROCEDURES AND ANALYSIS

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Introduction: Regardless of whether the sector is the ICU or the emergency room, something that differentiates nursing professionals when it comes to saving lives is their unquestionable preparation. With this in mind, the importance of the role of nursing in the early diagnosis of patients in neurological emergencies is conspicuous. **Objective:** To highlight the importance of early identification in neurological emergencies and the role of nursing in this process. **Methodology:** This is an integrative literature review, with a reflexive, descriptive and qualitative analysis. Eight articles were used from the following journals: Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO), Latin American and Caribbean Health Sciences Literature (LILACS) and Biomedcentral (BMC) **Results (Concluded):** Neurological emergencies need to be identified early so that the patient's quality of life after the procedure is better guaranteed, it is notorious how much this quality of life increases when the procedures are carried out by a nursing team that has the necessary skills regarding the process, nurses with specialized training in ICU and/or urgency and emergency are the professionals who work best in patient safety centers, Knowledge and technical preparation are crucial when managing patients in this situation, from visual inspection and physical examination at the time of anamnesis, to identification and continuous monitoring in the ICU. It is also important to combine multidisciplinary strategies with the investigative precepts stemming from the London protocol, so that there is a macro analysis of the clinical incident and not just focus on the failure. **Final considerations:** It is extremely important for the nursing team to be aware of their responsibility in this whole process. Neurological emergencies are complicated by their difficult prognosis, since the therapeutic window and the correct procedures are small. This process is essential both for the work of the nursing team and for the quality of life of the patients who are present there.

Keywords: Care. Emergency. ICU.

Thematic Area: Neurological Emergencies.